

INTEGRATING VECTOR OVERLAY INFORMATION INTO NAVAL DIGITAL MAP SYSTEMS

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Abstract

The US Navy's aviation platforms rely on cockpit moving-map displays to provide an accurate geospatial representation of a mission area to the warfighter to enhance situational awareness and improve mission effectiveness. Older digital map systems would simply display digitized, paper aeronautical charts to pilots and navigators. Navy systems now utilize the Tactical Aircraft Moving Map Capability (TAMMAC) as the common digital mapping system (DMS) for naval fixed wing aircraft. TAMMAC provides the enhanced capability to support digital terrain elevation data and imagery, in addition to digitized aeronautical charts. As technology has progressed, a newer model of TAMMAC provides advanced capabilities, including the ability to support vector overlay features integrated with other avionics functions in the DMS.

Scientists at the Naval Research Laboratory (NRL) have experience processing and compiling DMS data, as well as applying human factors principles to improve display design and facilitate pilots' and mission planners' comprehension of complex geospatial data. The goal is to help close the gap in enabling the extended capability of mission-specific vector overlays and to study its use to improve aircrew performance. This paper discusses prototype software developed by NRL that leverages several existing mission support software tools to select and prepare test datasets. The paper also evaluates test results from using these datasets within the DMS and proposes future work motivated by our findings.

Introduction

Pilots and navigators use mission planning software to select the desired geospatial information for a region and compile that information into a specific format required by the aircraft display hardware. The source data for this geographic information primarily consists of raster databases, including aeronautical charts, satellite imagery and

terrain elevation data. To further enhance these digital map products, support for customized display of various vector overlay features has been added. Though this feature is not yet widely implemented, it provides a means to include more pertinent, mission-specific information, including vertical obstructions, tactical symbology, MIL-STD-2525B symbology, Digital Aeronautical Flight Information Files (DAFIF) [1], and WEZOT (Weapons Engagement Zone Tool). Mission-specific information can also be added as vector overlays to represent routes, troop movements and kill boxes, depicted as local points and draw file objects.

TAMMAC Overview

TAMMAC provides advanced operational capability to enhance rotary and fixed wing aircraft operation effectiveness and survivability [2]. The function of TAMMAC is to provide the aircrew with an easily assimilated graphical presentation of the aircraft's present position and the relative positions of targets, threats, terrain features, planned mission flight path, no fly zones, safe bases and other objects. Increased mission effectiveness and survivability arise from improved situational awareness, reduced crew workload and enhanced capability for precision navigation, targeting, and obstacle avoidance. Advanced map capabilities that enhance these functions include presentation of contour lines, slope shading, dynamic elevation banding, threat intervisibility, cultural features, variable scaling, overlays, and mission re-planning.

TAMMAC consists of a DMS and an Advanced Memory Unit (AMU) connected via a high-speed interface. The DMS and the AMU are controlled via a 1553 multiplex bus. The DMS receives map data for storage into its bulk memory via the high-speed interface from the AMU. Using aircraft position data received via 1553 and map data from its bulk memory, the DMS generates digital moving map images and provides them to the displays. In addition to serving as the means to load map data into the aircraft, the AMU is also used to load mission

initialization data into the aircraft and to store mission and maintenance data that has been collected during flight. Operational Flight Program (OFP) loading is accomplished using the 1553 mux bus. Personal Computer Memory Card International Association (PCMCIA) cards are the media used to transfer data between the aircraft and the ground stations. The Joint Mission Planning system (JMPS) is used by the USN/USMC operational community to write mission initialization and map data (Compressed ARC Digitized Raster Graphics (CADRG) [3], Digital Terrain Elevation Data (DTED), Controlled Image Base (CIB) [4], etc.) to PCMCIA cards and process mission data that is collected in flight. Aircraft platforms that employ TAMMAC are: F/A-18 C/D, F/A-18 E/F, AV-8B, UH-1Y, and AH-1Z.

Processing Overview

As an introduction to the work flow of this prototype development, this section presents a high level walk through of the steps taken to add vector overlay information to the TAMMAC DMS. The method provided to achieve this capability in TAMMAC involves digitally packaging the vector overlay objects with underlying geospatial information which is then loaded onto the DMS. The types of geospatial information collected depend on whether a theater or mission build is generated. A theater build tends to be a larger set of geospatial information (limited to approximately 3GB) that contains data designed to support a general mission area while a mission build is much smaller (often less than 256 MB) and usually contains very specialized geospatial information that is tailored to support a specific mission and is generally used in conjunction with theater data.

Both theater and mission builds support the addition of vector overlay objects to the underlying map data. Applicable geospatial information that is supported by TAMMAC can be loaded into a mission planning support application where tools are provided to manage both standardized and custom vector overlay object information. Once the overlay information has been imported and modified for mission needs, a Harris Corporation developed standalone application known as the TOPS (TAMMAC Object Preprocessing Software) tool [5] is applied. The TOPS tool is used to convert vector overlay data from their native file formats into a

format supported by the TAMMAC hardware. The re-formatted files are then combined with an additional file, called a vector settings file, and packed into a theater or mission map build before being transferred to the TAMMAC DMS. The vector settings file allows for further customization of the display characteristics for each type of vector overlay object. These settings are chosen and stored using the standalone application Vector Settings Tool [6], also developed by the Harris Corporation.

In the final step, all of the geospatial information, including the processed vector object files and vector settings files are transferred into the Moving Map Composer Personal Computer (MMCP) application [7], developed by NRL. MMCP compiles all the geospatial information into either a theater or mission map build. The map build can then be transferred into the TAMMAC DMS via PCMCIA cards. The following sections will outline each of these major steps and present more detailed explanations of each part of the processing.

Collecting Initial Map Data

For the prototype experiment, a theater map build was to be tested and map data was chosen that would encompass the Point Mugu Naval Air Station and China Lake Test Range of California. Two standard National Geospatial Intelligence Agency (NGA) databases, CADRG and 5m resolution CIB, were obtained from the NGA NIPRnet website. Three distinct scales of CADRG were used for this prototype: (1) Jet Navigation Charts (JNC) at a scale of 1:2M; (2) Joint Operations Graphics (JOG) at a scale of 1:250K; (3) Tactical Pilotage Charts (TPC) at a scale of 1:500K. DAFIF Edition 7 was also obtained from NGA to provide an initial test of the display of standardized vector aeronautical information as a standardized vector overlay object.

Creating Vector Overlays

This section discusses the use of the mission planning application to generate additional vector overlays. Mission planning tools allow users to create, position, and set the display behavior of custom vector overlay objects. Once editing is complete, the objects are saved to a custom drawing file format [8]. To make sure that custom vector overlays are placed in the correct location, raster databases such as CADRG or CIB are displayed as

the underlying map so that overlays can be properly placed relative to important features.

Loading Geospatial Information in Mission Planning

Loading map data in mission planning is accomplished via the Map Data Manager tool. Traverse the main menu to Map | Map Data Manager and then click on the “Paths” tab as shown in Figure 1 to establish the path to the sources. Geospatial data is made available in mission planning by allowing the user to maintain a catalog of file paths which point to the locations of available geospatial data.

Figure 1. Mission Planning Map Data Manager

As paths are selected, a validation is performed and only those paths that are properly formatted are added to the catalog. Once a particular path has been validated, the geospatial information can then be displayed.

The mission planning application provides a DAFIF import tool that can be accessed from the menu by choosing “Tools | Data Administration | DAFIF Importer...”. The tool first validates the format of the new database and then allows the user to import the DAFIF Edition 7 information for display. This process provides the method to display a raster map (CADRG or CIB) background with a standardized set of aeronautical vector overlays (DAFIF) in mission planning.

Adding Vector Overlays in Mission Planning

This section discusses the types of vector objects that can be added and the guidelines for ensuring that the objects and settings chosen fit the requirements for the TAMMAC DMS.

For the vector objects created in mission planning and saved as drawing files, special considerations need to be made because only a subset of the object types and property settings are currently supported within the TAMMAC DMS. For example, a wide range of font styles and sizes can be associated with drawing files. However, the TAMMAC DMS only supports one font which does not match exactly with any of the fonts and text sizes available during mission planning. This and other differences can be managed by following the guidelines provided in the Database Design Document for the TAMMAC map[9]. Documentation suggests choosing ‘Arial Unicode MS’ as the best approximation for the TAMMAC font style and provides a lookup table that maps mission planning font sizes to the appropriate TAMMAC text display sizes. This lookup table suggests that a text object’s font size between 18 and 22 in mission planning equates to a 100% text size factor in the TAMMAC DMS. Another consideration is the line width translations for lines and polygons since 8 line widths are supported for drawing files while TAMMAC implements only 4. The TAMMAC Database Design Document should be referenced very closely to help ensure that what is shown in mission planning will be closely approximated in the TAMMAC DMS.

Using Drawing Tools in Mission Planning

Once the geospatial information has been configured using the Map Data Manager, the Overlay Toolkit, shown in Figure 2, can be used to create, customize and position various vector overlay objects. The toolkit supports the creation and configuration of object types such as text, line, poly line, polygon, rectangle, ellipse, axis of advance and bulls eye [8]. Only text and rectangle objects were used to test this basic functionality.

Figure 2. Mission Planning Overlay Toolkit

For the test dataset, 24 box shaped polygons were created and arranged in a gridded pattern. The grid was designed to cover the area that extends from Point Mugu Naval Air Station to the China Lake Test Range of California to emulate a killbox pattern. Each box also had an upper and lower text label added in order to test the replication of vector overlay text information between mission planning and the TAMMAC DMS.

The boxes in the grid were drawn by selecting the rectangle drawing tool from the overlay toolkit toolbar. Then, the mouse was used to point and click at the starting position and dragged to stretch the box to the desired size before releasing the mouse button. Once drawn, the individual properties of each rectangle were customized using the rectangle properties dialog shown in Figure 3a. The borders were set to red to provide a good contrast with the underlying map data and the fill style was disabled so that no fill would be added. This resulted in a simple but distinct outline for each box. Although each box had the option of having a label created as part of the polygon object, this option was left blank so that labels could be added using the text object tool. This approach was chosen so that multiple labels could be added to each box and each label could have different display behavior settings. This was also an advantage since text created with the text object tool has more options for customizing display behavior than if added using the label property of the polygon box tool.

For each of the polygon boxes in the grid, two text objects were added using the text object tool. Red was chosen for the text color to maintain conformity with box outline color and to provide high contrast between the drawing file overlay and background raster map. The text objects were positioned such that one label was near the top and the other near the bottom of a box. To get a basic understanding of how the text objects are affected by various settings, the lower label was marked as “FIXED” (Figure 3b) while the upper label was marked “SCALE” (Figure 3c). The text for each label was also padded with X’s in order to make each label span the entire width of each box. This was done so that the stationary polygon lines could serve as a good reference to compare the effects of different scale and zoom levels on the text objects.

Once all of the text and polygon objects were created, they were saved in a drawing file and pre-processed for the TAMMAC DMS using the TOPS tool.

Figure 3. Drawing File Object Settings

Pre-Formatting With TOPS Tool

The TOPS application was designed for the sole purpose of pre-formatting vector data for use in vector enabled TAMMAC DMS. Once all of the vector overlay data has been created and/or imported, it is processed by the TOPS tool which pre-processes the vector objects in the required format for the TAMMAC DMS.

The TOPS tool locates input datasets by reading the contents of the “FileList.txt” file. Any files listed within this file will be included in the pre-processing. The file extensions supported within the TOPS tools and their associated data types are listed in Table 1. For this prototype, only DAFIF and custom drawing files were pre-processed. Once the filenames for each vector overlay feature have been added, the path to the “FileList.txt” file is set as the “File List Path” within the TOPS GUI as shown in Figure 4.

Table 1. TOPS Tool File Extensions

Data Type	File Extension
DAFIF	.txt
Vertical Obstructions	.shp
Tactical Symbols	.tgf
Local Points	.lpt
Drawing Files	.drw

In addition, an optional “Rules.txt” file can be created, as described in the TOPS User’s Guide to indicate how the TAMMAC DMS should handle cases where the amount of vector overlays surpasses the allowable limits within the TAMMAC vector map capability. TOPS separates the vector map objects into 1:250k gridded shape files with each grid file having a specific limit of point objects and line segments per file. The rules that are added to “Rules.txt” prioritize what data will be kept in cases where the object count surpasses these limits. This file is not required if these limits will not be reached or if the default rules, as defined in the TOPS User’s Guide are acceptable. In either case, once the file is configured its location can be set in the TOPS GUI under the “Rules File Path” as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. TOPS Tool Settings

Another way to limit the amount of vector map objects is to limit the bounding area. The bounding area is defined by specifying the north, east, south, and west corners of the area to be processed. These values are defined in the TOPS GUI and are used as a geospatial filter while the vector map objects are being processed. When a bounding area is set, only the information needed for those bounds are processed.

Once all of the inputs have been specified and the output directory has been set, the “Process” button is clicked and all of the vector overlay objects are processed into gridded shape files that are supported by the TAMMAC DMS. The number of shape files varies depending on the number and type of vector overlay objects, the rules file, and the bounding area defined. Once the processing has completed successfully two notifications will be displayed. The first notification alerts the user that processing is complete and lists the number of rules that were applied to the data. The second notification is a reminder to the user to check the automated log file that is generated and placed in the output directory.

Reviewing the contents of the log file is critical to ensure that all vector objects have been properly processed by the TOPS tool. If certain objects have not been processed because they are either not supported or because object count limits have been exceeded, the only means of identifying the missing objects is by examining the log file. The log file will list any warnings related to omitted objects and/or actions taken to substitute default values for unsupported attribute settings. The log file will also provide another warning if more gridded shape files have been generated from the set of vector objects than can be supported for the vector map capability via a mission build. This warning is a signal to the user that a theater build would have to be generated instead of a mission build in order to support the required number of gridded shape files.

After final preparation of the vector overlay objects has been completed, the files are ready to be packaged together with other geospatial information into a theater map build.

Choosing Vector Object Behavior

The final level of customization that affects the display of vector overlay objects in the TAMMAC DMS is provided by the vector settings file. The vector settings file maintains the entire modifiable vector object settings allowed within the TAMMAC DMS. Some of the key user-selectable vector settings include enabling which vector objects are displayed; applicable TAMMAC scales when the vector object is displayed, priority of vector object type, color, font size, and fill pattern [9]. The vector settings file is a distinct TAMMAC configuration file

included as part of a theater map build. This file provides the means of modifying the display of vector overlay objects in the TAMMAC DMS without having to modify the DMS OFP.

The vector settings file is created and edited using the Vector Settings Tool which presents an organized and helpful interface for selecting display settings. To build the vector settings file, the Vector Settings Tool was run to create a default file named VECTRSET.HRS. For the prototype, most of the default settings were unchanged. As shown in Figure 5, the display of drawing file objects was enabled at offset 238. Then, a few select settings were made to display text size at 100% when the scale is above 1:100K and at 50% when the scale is above 1:250K and to hide it all together when the scale is above 1:1M. Also the priority of display objects were set to 100 (highest priority possible). Other settings were changed to test the display of DAFIF data. For this prototype, only military, joint use and limited facilities airports were to be displayed. Settings were also configured to display DAFIF symbol size as 75% above a scale of 1:200K, 50% above 1:1M and to hide DAFIF labels above 1:1M. Finally, a value of 0 was entered for the “Minimum Useable Runway” setting which indicates that all runways are displayed regardless of length.

The final vector settings that were adjusted were at the bottom of the file and are used to limit the number of primitives that will be displayed. Since our primary vector overlay objects were drawing file and DAFIF, we set each to 200 for this test.

Organizing Map Build Input

The final link to demonstrating vector overlay capability in the TAMMAC DMS is to add the TOPS and Vector Settings output to a theater map build. This section discusses the last few steps for preparing vector overlay objects for the TAMMAC DMS using the MMCPC application. MMCPC is an NRL-developed application that is used for designing and constructing theater map builds those builds into a ready format for the TAMMAC DMS. MMCPC was leveraged so that the additional vector overlay information could be included in the theater map build with the underlying raster geospatial information (i.e. CADRG or CIB). MMCPC enables a user to import and view the raster geospatial information (e.g. CADRG, CIB) used in the

TAMMAC DMS for selection and use in map builds. In MMCPC, the import process is called “logging”. For this prototype, the both CADRG and CIB data was logged into the MMCPC application. This is accomplished by choosing “Log | Log Source” from the main menu which will present the dialog shown in Figure 5. With the dialog, the user browses to the location of each dataset where each is validated and then approved for “logging”. Logging the map data is required for any information that will be packaged into a theater map build.

Figure 5. MMCPC Data Log Dialog

The next step is typically “composing” an area with data that has been logged into MMCPC. However, since we are including additional vector overlay objects there are a couple extra steps to be taken first. To test the vector overlay capability in the TAMMAC DMS, the MMCPC code was modified to support the extra vector overlay objects in TAMMAC theater map builds. To keep the prototype development simple, the application checks for additional input in a system folder named “tivo” during the map build process. Any files that MMCPC finds in that directory (i.e. vector overlay objects), are automatically processed along with the raster geospatial information and included as part of a theater map build. For this functionality to work properly, all of the output files generated from the TOPS application, other than the log file, are copied to the tivo folder. When the theater map build is generated in MMCPC, those additional files are included in the TAMMAC map theater “arc.dat” file. The arc.dat file is a file specifically formatted to hold all of the geospatial information including raster data and vector overlay objects. Another necessary step is to include two extra configuration files. The first file is supplied by Harris Corp named “TEXTLINE.HRS”. The second is the “VECTRSET.HRS” created earlier using the Vector Settings Tool. Without these files, the TAMMAC

system will run in non-enhanced mode and not display vector overlay objects.

Creating Theater Map Builds

The next step is to create a map composition. This composition is used to create a map build.

The basic way to create a composition is to start by adding geospatial information that has been logged into MMCP. This can be done by using the main menu and selecting “Compose | Include Coverage | Logged Source”. This menu item loads a dialog that presents all of the available map data to the user. The user then selects from the list what data will be included in the composition and ultimately the theater map build. For this example, all of the logged data is intended for creating a map build so all of the available data sources are selected as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. MMCP Include Logged Sources

MMCP provides a map to view the location and source data so the raster geospatial information can be reviewed. MMCP provides a map display that shows a boxed outline for each data file. There are tools included for selecting and deselecting coverages of data from each type and scale of map and to display the contents of each raster file. Figure 7 shows an example of the coverage map for the available CADRG map data at the 1:250K scale. After reviewing the available data for each of the scales and dataset types, the next step is to save the composition and give it a name. The next step once the map composition is complete is to create a map build. A future enhancement for MMCP would be to support the graphical display of the vector overlay

object output from the TOPS tool for additional validation.

Figure 7. MMCP CADRG Coverage

Theater map builds are created from compositions and, for this prototype, also includes the vector overlay objects found in the “tivo” folder. The theater map build begins by opening the composition that references the geospatial information to be included. To open the map composition in MMCP, select “File | Open” from the main menu and then choose the composition from the list. Next Choose “Build | Build Map” from the main menu and the dialog shown in Figure 8 will be presented. A default name for the Theater build is given and “theater” is the default “Build Type”. For the prototype, the defaults were accepted and the theater build was created by clicking the “Ok” button.

Figure 8. MMCP Build Map

The output of a theater map build consists of two files: dir.dat and arc.dat. As MMCP goes through the build process, it first processes all the geospatial information referenced in the composition and the entire set of vector overlay objects in the “tivo” folder. Finally, the required configuration files including the VECTRSET.HRS file are applied. As each file is compiled as part of the “arc.dat” file, MMCP places an entry in the dir.dat file that consists of the filename and an offset to the

beginning of the file contents in the arc.dat file. The end result is a file that contains the contents of all of the raster and vector overlay files (i.e. arc.dat), and a listing of all the files and their location within arc.dat (i.e. dir.dat).

Writing Map Builds

Writing a theater map build to a PCMCIA card for use in the TAMMAC DMS is performed through MMPCPC. The theater map build is directly transferred to a pcmcia card which is then ready for transfer to the TAMMAC DMS via the AMU.

In the case of writing a theater map build to a pcmcia card, MMPCPC provides the functionality by choosing “Build | Write Theater Map” from the main menu. MMPCPC then prompts the user to select the appropriate theater map build to use and for the serial number of the pcmcia card to be used as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. MMPCPC Build Map

Test Results

The prototype theater map data constructed through MMPCPC consisted of the following geospatial information covering a region from Pt. Mugu, CA to the China Lake Test Range:

- CADRG – Jet Navigation Chart (1:2M)
- CADRG – Tactical Pilotage Chart (1:500k)
- CADRG – Joint Operations Graphics (1:250k)
- CIB – Controlled Image Base 5 meter res.
- DAFIF – Military, Joint, Limited Airfields (all runway lengths)
- Draw Files – Simulated Killbox Grid with Text Annotations

Figure 10 shows an example in mission planning of the 1:500k CADRG map with DAFIF and annotated killbox overlays.

Figure 10. CADRG (1:500k) with Vector Overlays

Verification tests were performed in the TAMMAC simulator lab at Pt. Mugu Naval Air Station. No pictures from the verification in the lab were allowed to be taken. However, all vector overlay objects were correctly displayed, although the fonts were not exactly replicated in the TAMMAC DMS (as expected). It was noted that the fixed scale text for the annotated drawing files (Figure 3b) always maintained the same font size regardless of the selected TAMMAC DMS scale setting. So, while the killbox graphic would always scale appropriately with a change to the TAMMAC DMS scale setting, the fixed scale text would not adjust. This behavior would result in text appearing far too big relative to the scale of the map when zoomed out. The behavior of the “scale to map” text maintained a better relationship relative to a change in TAMMAC map scale setting, although the scaling of the text was not exactly a one-to-one relationship, and could become unreadable as the font became too small. Further investigation is needed to determine appropriate font size mapping in mission planning to render its nearest equivalent font in the TAMMAC DMS.

For the DAFIF overlays, the selected types of DAFIF airfields were properly drawn over the CADRG raster equivalent airfield graphics with a blue circle, runway, and the airfield identifier. However, when CIB was displayed as the raster background map, only the airfield identifier was present with the blue circle and runway graphic absent. This behavior would be expected since CIB is a much larger scale (i.e. higher resolution) than the CADRG data. To reduce the amount of overlay

clutter, DAFIF (when displayed in conjunction with CIB) only displays the airfield identifier.

Observations

The prototype development was successfully implemented using a variety of standalone mission planning and vector processing tools. Vector overlay behaviors must be carefully chosen to render the expected results in the TAMMAC DMS. Specifically, the method in which vector overlay text is constructed in mission planning has a direct effect on the display of those vector objects in TAMMAC. The inability to directly map font sizes between mission planning and the TAMMAC DMS equivalent can be problematic. While the vector setting file provides a powerful method to affect the behaviors of the vector overlay objects in TAMMAC, very small changes to this file can significantly alter the way vector overlays are displayed. Further, it would also appear that vector overlay behavior can change based on the type of background raster map displayed in TAMMAC. However, this may also be an effect of a vector setting for the vector overlay object that was not noted in this prototype experiment. Overall, the vector overlay capability of the TAMMAC DMS can be a powerful tool for the pilot, but great care must be taken in the development and construction of the vector overlay objects, especially for vector text overlays and setting parameters within the vector setting file.

Future Work

Proposed future work would include the following:

- Develop specialized drawing editor that limits vector object creation to TAMMAC compatible objects.
- Consolidate all standalone functions under a single user-friendly application.
- Test more vector overlay object types and settings.
 - Determine functional operation.
 - Determine most helpful objects and settings.
 - Develop guidelines for creation of objects and settings for best results.

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Acknowledgements

This research was funded by the Office of Naval Research, Program Element 602435N, through the Naval Research Laboratory 6.2 Base Program. The authors also wish to gratefully acknowledge Mr. Keith Kane (TAMMAC IPT lead), Mr. Patrick Clausius (PMA209 TAMMAC APMSE), and Mr. Alfredo Fajardo (TAMMAC Mission Planning Lead), Ms. Maivan Ly (TAMMAC Mission Planning) and Ms. Lisa Chan (Harris Corp.) for their support.

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*30th Digital Avionics Systems Conference
October 16-20, 2011*